

Polarographic Study of Zn(II)-Acetylacetonate System vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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Polarographic behaviour of Zn(II) has been studied in the presence of increasing amounts of acetylacetonate (0.01–0.08M) at a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1$ (NaNO₃) and at constant pH 6. The reduction of Zn(II) has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in the presence of acetylacetonate. $E_{1/2}$ gets shifted to more cathodic potentials with increasing [Acetylacetonate]. The reversible half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}^r$) has been calculated by Gellings method. Zn(II) forms three successive complex species with acetylacetonate viz., [Zn(Acac)]⁺, Zn(Acac)₂ and [Zn(Acac)₃]⁻ with stability constants $\log \beta_1=5$, $\log \beta_2=10$, $\log \beta_3=14.30$ at 25°. The percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of ligand concentration has also been presented. The kinetic parameters (α , n_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been calculated by Koutecky's method.

BRANICA^{1,2} and coworkers have undertaken polarographic investigations on acetylacetonate complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II). However, the polarographic study of Zn(II) acetylacetonate system has not been taken up so far. With this aim in view the present study dealing with the polarography of Zn(II)-acetylacetonate system has been undertaken.

Experimental

Solutions of ZnCl₂ and NaNO₃ were prepared from reagent grade chemicals in conductivity water. Acetylacetonate was of E. Merck, G. R. grade and its aqueous solution was used as ligand. The concentration of Zn(II) in each case was kept at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$. The concentration of acetylacetonate was calculated from the pH and the pK value³⁻⁵ (8.95) of acetylacetonate. As no maximum was encountered in the present study, use of a suppressor was avoided.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL-50) was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions to remove the dissolved oxygen. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1M NaNO₃, open circuit): $m=1.673$ mg/sec., $t=4.04$ sec., $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=1.778$ mg^{2/3} sec^{1/6}, $h_{corr}=63$ cm. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon⁶ using d.m.e. as cathode and the mercury pool as anode. The formula used was

$$n_2 = n_1 \left(\frac{\Delta i_{d, caa}}{i_{d, caa}} \right) \left(\frac{i_{d, sub}}{\Delta i_{d, sub}} \right) \frac{V_1 C_1}{V_2 C_2}$$

where $i_{d, caa}$ is the original diffusion current (corrected for the residual current) for cadmium solution, V_1 its

volume, C_1 its concentration and $\Delta i_{d, caa}$ is the change in diffusion current produced by the electrolysis. $i_{d, sub}$, $\Delta i_{d, sub}$, V_2 and C_2 are the corresponding quantities for the solution of the substance. n_1 and n_2 are the number of electrons involved in the reduction of cadmium and substance at d.m.e. respectively. As the concentration and volume in respect of cadmium and substance were the same $V_1=V_2=0.3$ ml; $C_1=C_2=1 \times 10^{-3} M$, the last factor in the above equation is unity. In the present system n was found to be 2.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of the solution containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Zn(II) and 0.08 M acetylacetonate were taken at different pH values. It was observed that the negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ was maximum at pH 6. On further increasing the pH, Zn(II) gets precipitated and hence pH 6 was chosen for studying the complex formation between Zn(II) and acetylacetonate. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 0.01 to 0.08 M. In each case a single well defined diffusion-controlled wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ were found to be linear and passing through the origin, thereby showing the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction.

On applying various criteria of irreversibility⁷⁻¹⁰ it has been found that the reduction of Zn(II) in the presence of increasing concentrations of acetylacetonate is irreversible. However, in the absence of the ligand the reduction of Zn(II) is quasi-reversible.

Lal and Christian¹¹ and recently Zutshi and Gupta¹² have suggested a method for determining the composition and stability constants of consecutively formed complex species, undergoing irreversible reduction at d.m.e by determining the value of reversible half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}^r$), by Gellings¹³ method. This

method has been followed in the present study and the $E_{1/2}^r$ values as a function of [Acetylacetonate] have been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Zn(II)-ACETYLACETONATE SYSTEM $\mu=0.1$ (NaNO₃), pH 6, TEMP. $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

[H Acac] M	[Acac ⁻] $\times 10^5$ M	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV
0	0	1.00	0.98	44.0
0.01	1.122	1.02	1.01	80.6
0.02	2.245	1.04	1.02	80.6
0.04	4.467	1.06	1.025	85.7
0.06	6.607	1.08	1.04	85.0
0.08	8.976	1.10	1.06	44.0

A plot of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs-log [Acetylacetonate] (Fig. 1) is found to be a smooth curve thereby showing formation

Fig. 1. $-E_{1/2}^r$ vs $-\log [Acac^-]$ for Zn(II) Acetylacetonate system.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a AND $k_{f,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Zn(II)-ACETYLACETONATE SYSTEM

[H Acac] M	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
0		
0.01	0.86	3.98×10^{-15}
0.02	0.74	9.22×10^{-14}
0.04	0.74	4.12×10^{-13}
0.06	0.61	1.56×10^{-12}
0.08	0.54	1.78×10^{-12}

of consecutive complexes. DeFord and Hume's¹⁴ method modified by Irving¹⁵ has been applied for the calculation of composition and stability constants of the complexes.

An analysis of $F_j[X]$ functions (Fig. 2) reveals the formation of three successive complex species viz., $[Zn(Acac)]^+$, $[Zn(Acac)_2]$ and $[Zn(Acac)_3]^-$ with stability constants $\log \beta_1 = 5$, $\log \beta_2 = 10$ and $\log \beta_3 = 14.30$.

Fig. 2. $F_j[X]$ vs $[Acac^-]$ for Zn(II) Acetylacetonate system

- — $F_0[X]$
- — $F_1[X]$
- △ — $F_2[X]$
- ▲ — $F_3[X]$

Fig. 3. Percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of $[Acac^-]$

- ▲ — Zn^{2+}
- — $[Zn(Acac)]^+$
- — $[Zn(Acac)_2]$
- — $[Zn(Acac)_3]^-$

The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ of the electrode reaction have been calculated by Koutecky's method and the values have been listed in Table 2.

The percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of [Acetylacetonate] has been presented in Fig. 3.

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